

INCENTIVE
CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

D2.4

Activities of Citizen Science Hubs

University of Twente

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Abbreviations

AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece)
CS	Citizen Science
CSH	Citizen Science Hub
RPFO	Research Performing and Funding Organisation
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
UAB	Autonomous University of Barcelona (Spain)
UT	University of Twente (Netherlands)
VG TU	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Lithuania)
QH	Quadruple Helix

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

About INCENTIVE.....	7
About the activities of the CSHs.....	7
Conclusions.....	7

1. INTRODUCTION 8

1.1 About INCENTIVE.....	8
1.2 About the Citizen Science Hubs and their activities	10
1.3 About this report	11

2. DEFINING THE ACTIVITIES TO BE PURSUED BY THE CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS..... 12

2.1 Envisioned activities by the Citizen Science Hubs.....	12
2.2 Insights into preferred activities	13
2.2.1 <i>Learnings from setting the scene.....</i>	13
2.2.2 <i>Learnings from the Co-Creation Workshop.....</i>	14
2.2.3 <i>Learnings from the Governance Structure and Operating Models.....</i>	14
2.2.4 <i>Learnings from Monitoring & Evaluation Framework.....</i>	16
2.3 Methodology for CSH activities	17

3. ACTIVITIES DEFINED BY EACH CITIZEN SCIENCE HUB..... 23

3.1 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTh)	23
3.2 Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB).....	24
3.3 University of Twente (UT).....	25
3.4 Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VGTU)	26

4. CONCLUSIONS..... 27

REFERENCES..... 28

List of Figures

Figure 1: Distribution of the pilot CSHs at the four European RPFOs	8
Figure 2: INCENTIVE relates the principles of RRI to Citizen Science	9

List of Tables

Table 1: Proposed activities by the CSHs per RPFO	15
Table 2: Proposed M&E activities by the CSHs*	17
Table 3: Activity clusters of the CSHs	20

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

About INCENTIVE

The 3-year European project INCENTIVE (Grant Agreement No 101005330) mobilises citizens and stakeholders to become agents of scientific change through their direct participation. At the same time, Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) are encouraged to open their doors to citizens and equip them with the necessary tools for enhanced scientific skills. INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science (CS) through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs (CSHs) throughout the EU.

About the activities of the CSHs

This deliverable 2.4 presents a methodology for activities of the CSHs (outcome of Task T2.4). In Section 2, we present a methodology for defining activities considering the establishment of the CSH from getting started towards the more permanent phase. We discuss the following clusters of activities in order of development of the CSHs;

1. Monitoring and evaluation;
2. Awareness raising;
3. R&I co-creation;
4. Capacity building;
5. Mutual learning and networking.

Furthermore, we discern levels of activities to be considered when establishing the CSH: strategic tactical and operational. In Section 3, we offer overviews of what the piloting RPFOS have shared on their preferred activities.

Conclusions

The report contributes to support the RPFOS to move towards the piloting phase by providing insights into what has been identified so far regarding the CSH's activities, and what the various participating RPFOS consider to be necessary.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 About INCENTIVE

Europe's Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) have a crucial role to play as agents of institutional change towards firmly grounding Responsible Research Innovation (RRI) in our society. The successful fulfilment of this challenging, yet highly significant, role calls for the values of RRI to be well-embedded into RPFOS governance, as well as their operation with greater and more systematic participation of citizens and all R&I stakeholders. The 3-year European project INCENTIVE (Grant Agreement No 101005330) mobilises citizens and stakeholders to become agents of scientific change through their direct participation. At the same time, the participating institutes and universities are encouraged to open their doors to citizens and equip them with the necessary tools for enhanced scientific skills. Our ambition is to co-create Citizen Science Hubs (CSHs) for (a new generation of citizen) scientists and a new institutional European paradigm that bridges science with society.

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science (CS) through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of CSHs in four RPFOS (see Figure 1):

- Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Lithuania);
- University of Twente (the Netherlands);
- Autonomous University of Barcelona (Spain), and;
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece).

Figure 1: Distribution of the pilot CSHs at the four European RPFOS

Within INCENTIVE, the aim is to power European RPFOS to embrace Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) through the paradigm of Citizen Science – a democratic and collaborative way

of designing, implementing and monitoring scientific progress and technological growth. RRI describes scientific research and technological development processes aligning social, ecological and technological needs, and can be defined as:

"A transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products (in order to allow a proper embedding of scientific and technological advances in our society)." (Von Schomberg, 2013, p.19)

RRI involves conducting research to high ethical standards, ensuring gender equality and inclusion in the scientific community, investing policymakers with the responsibility to avoid harmful effects of innovation, engaging the communities affected by innovation and ensuring that they have the knowledge necessary to understand the implications by furthering science education and Open Access. It should be understood as *"A strategy of stakeholders to become mutually responsive to each other and anticipate research and innovation outcomes underpinning the "grand challenges" of our time for which they share responsibility."* (Von Schomberg, 2013, p.1)

In practice, RRI started to innovate responsibly, considering ethics, implications for society, and issues that might arise for communities. It implies that working on innovation requires that we are inclusive and that the way we work is easily accessible to stakeholders and communities. In INCENTIVE, the ambition is to accelerate the transition of the pilot RPOs to be more inclusive, open and strive towards democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of RRI, which are shown below (Figure 2). We seek to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes about how to create and operate their own CS Hub with the aim of securing a sustainable future.

Figure 2: INCENTIVE relates the principles of RRI to Citizen Science

In the first phases of the project, we tailored the governance and operating models of these hubs to their unique institutional specificities and regional ecosystems of R&I stakeholders, before putting them to the test to drive institutional change through a series of RRI-grounding actions conducted with and for society (CS, co-creation of public policies, R&I agenda setting, etc.). As each institution displayed different levels of citizen science maturity and diverging regional specificities, INCENTIVE's work showcased that facilitating deeper adoption of RRI through CSHs is achievable in diverse settings, thus strengthening the project's replicability.

Ultimately, we aim to strengthen the capacity of RPFOS to implement the sustainable institutional changes necessary to foster RRI and increase their systematic collaboration with other actors. The CSHs will be integrated into each RPFOS, dedicated to participatory Research and Innovation (R&I), with and for citizens. Through empowering internal and external stakeholders in the co-creation of new knowledge, stakeholders will spur valuable interactions that will help to embed the RRI keys within each organisation. As such, INCENTIVE intends for these hubs to be levers of change within each participating institution, contributing to an improved uptake of the RRI keys, expansion of citizen science and equipping the institution to better fulfil their social mission by meaningfully contributing to multilevel development.

1.2 About the Citizen Science Hubs and their activities

As introduced, we aim to establish four CSHs during the lifespan of the project. So far, we have been mapping, researching and co-creating the major elements of CSHs. Next, we are entering the phase of piloting the concept of the CSHs at the four RPFOS shown in Figure 1.

We have defined "Citizen Science Hub" as follows:

A Citizen Science Hub...

is a scientific organisation (or part of a scientific organisation) with the purpose to initiate, execute, promote and coordinate participatory Research and Innovation (R&I) with and for citizens. As such, Citizen Science Hubs based in Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) are tasked with empowering their internal and external stakeholders to co-create new knowledge in a transdisciplinary way, forging new stakeholder interactions and grounding Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in society.

Defining the activities of the CSHs is foreseen, which is the main objective of this report, in preparing for the piloting phase. In parallel to task 2.4, the governance structures and operation models will also be delivered (Task 2.2), as well as ways to incentivise stakeholders (Task 2.3). These three tasks together will provide the core elements to arrive at the Operational Plans per CSH that feeds the start of the piloting phase to commence mid-2022. The piloting phase will run until the end of 2023.

1.3 About this report

This report describes the methodology for defining the activities to be pursued by the Citizen Science Hubs, as well as the specific activities that will be carried out in the CSH of each RPFO. In doing so, we have collected the insights and knowledge generated so far within INCENTIVE, complemented with insights from other relevant sources outside of the project. With the report, we mainly intend to provide advice and guidance to the four piloting RPFOs. In Chapter 2, we present what insights in activities were already generated by earlier efforts in the project and included them into this chapter to provide a more in-depth analysis of how the activities could be defined. Furthermore, in this chapter, we propose a methodology for defining activities of the CSHs. In Chapter 3, we summarized the activities that we defined per CSH, hence providing the major input to the next phase of the project, leading to operational plans for each hub. Finally, Chapter 4 completes the report by describing its conclusions.

2. DEFINING THE ACTIVITIES TO BE PURSUED BY THE CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

2.1 Envisioned activities by the Citizen Science Hubs

The objective of Task 2.4 leading to this report was to define the activities of the Hubs to ground RRI in society, focusing on R&I co-creation.¹ The activities of the hubs were defined by UT with the support of the partners UAB, AUTH, VGTU, CC-CS and Q-PLAN. For this report, we collected input on the CSHs' activities as provided by the respective RPFOS in earlier actions in the project. We present a methodology and how this can be applied in the context of the respective CSHs. This will be further applied in WP3 which is covering the setting-up and operating of the CSHs; the project's piloting phase.

When defining activities for the hubs, we should keep in mind that we want to increase our understanding of how CS can include the key components of RRI by means of including citizens into every aspect of the R&I process. This includes from developing and defining the research problems and questions to collecting data, inputs and the management of research, up to how citizens can be included in and obtain access to the benefits of science and technology. Activities should not "simply" be welcoming citizens in academic data collection, but they must contribute to participatory Research and Innovation (R&I) stakeholder empowerment.

The essential meaning of activity is: "something that is done (...) for a particular purpose"². Hence, it is crucial to define the objectives and purposes of the CSH(s) before we define its activities. In the Introduction, we showed that the purpose of the CSH was to initiate, execute, promote and coordinate participatory Research and Innovation with and for citizens. CSHs are tasked with *empowering their stakeholders to co-create new knowledge in a transdisciplinary way and to be forging new stakeholder interactions and grounding Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in society*. The task adds to one of the core objectives of the project being: enhance the ability of citizen scientists to meaningfully participate in all facets of R&I and foster the development of communities around citizen science (O3).

It is foreseen in the project plan that the actions to be piloted by the CSHs will be co-defined with R&I stakeholders during the project. Over their course, the incentivisation and digital tools will stimulate public engagement, while also helping to gather meaningful evidence on societal, democratic, economic and scientific impacts of institutional changes. Therefore, being the units of action in the project, the CSHs are confronted with a challenging task to initiate and operate their piloting phase in their own contexts, while at the same time testing the tools from the project in action. CSH activities are going to be monitored using four methods, namely: (1) the collection of feedback from CS project participants through CS Project questionnaires; (2) the collection of data from various CS Hub activities through CS Hub report; (3) the collection of

¹ These activities are: R&I co-creation activities; Awareness raising activities; mutual learning and networking activities; capacity building activities; monitoring and assessment activities

² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/activity> (accessed 8 February 2022)

data regarding institutional changes through RPFO report, and (4) the collection of data on involved citizens' viewpoints through stakeholder interviews (Angelidou et al., 2022).

In the next section, we will provide an overview of the findings and input collected earlier in the project as to provide a basis for a methodology that define CSH activities. This is covered in the subsequent section.

2.2 Insights into preferred activities

2.2.1 Learnings from setting the scene

As to identify relevant insights captured earlier in the project, we first investigate WP1, on setting the scene. In Mapping the current landscape of citizen science initiatives and identifying good practices (Task 1.1), provided a review of the landscape of CS initiatives driven by RFPOs (Laboratory of Geoinformatics, 2021). This led to a couple of relevant indicators of success of CS initiatives:

- Support of the CS initiative by scientists well-known in the community who assume the role of "citizen science champions" and who can mobilise and promote the establishment of the CS initiative within an RPFO;
- The existence of a strong network and knowledge on the topic at local and national level, and the growing interest of the community in the scientific topic;
- Citizen participation by policy makers in connection with the availability of a funding support mechanism may serve as drivers and success factors for the establishment of a successful and promising CS initiative within an RPFO;
- The community familiarity with participatory or volunteering activities may increase the number of stakeholders and citizens involved and thus help spread the CS practice, increase the number of CS projects and set solid foundation for the sustainability of the CS initiative;
- The provision of infrastructure tools that facilitate the implementation of CS projects by the community members seems to be a key factor to facilitate the successful operation of a CS initiative.

The T1.1 review also gave insights about the challenges of CS initiatives driven by RFPOs such as:

- The active engagement and involvement of citizens. Having the right technical infrastructure and tools will serve as a driver for citizens to participate;
- Carrying out a multistakeholder CS initiative seems to require a well-defined organisational structure and role allocation from the beginning of its establishment.

With regards to the engagement of stakeholders, Task 1.3 - on the QH stakeholders' requirements and motivations - identified the enabling and hindering factors Quadruple Helix

stakeholders encountered regarding active engagement in the CSHs in the four national contexts (Psaltoglou et al., 2021). This has taught us that:

- The four countries strongly differ regarding the current social trends and perceptions vis-à-vis Citizen Science, as well as the role and limitations of the envisioned CSHs;
- The results show diversification of perceptions, in some instances quite strong, across the OH stakeholder groups;
- Depending on the country and the pre-existing level of Citizen Science maturity, the results provide a complicated network of factors that unlock or block participation in CS activities. These factors include, to name a few, political maturity, civic engagement, technological infrastructures, economic growth, culture of stakeholder collaboration, psychological stimulus, and surplus of resources.

2.2.2 Learnings from the Co-Creation Workshop

Let's now investigate WP2, on co-creating the Citizen Science Hubs, that started with one of INCENTIVE's first actions being the delivery of the Co-Creation Workshop (Task 2.1) to engage with the stakeholders of each RPF0. The workshop aimed to co-define the pivotal aspects of the governance and operation of the prospective CSHs. This task has been completed, including a deliverable reporting on the process and outcomes (Van den Berg et al., 2021). The participants concluded the Co-Creation Workshop by defining main (clusters of) activities for the preferred CSH. In general, the main (clusters of) activities that were addressed for preferred CSHs were:

- Research: Data collection, participatory science, engage with new researchers in CS, scientific methods, contributing to evidence-based research;
- Awareness & engagement: Stakeholder engagement, partnerships, agenda setting;
- Education: Training, lifelong learning, skills, scientific methods, and data collection.

During the Co-Creation Workshop, activities were mainly addressed at CSH level. Therefore, the outcomes are explained in more detail below where we report on the activities per RPF0 (Chapter 3 Activities defined by each Citizen Science Hub).

2.2.3 Learnings from the Governance Structure and Operating Models

Parallel to defining the activities for the CSHs (Task 2.4), runs task T2.2 that prepared Governance Structure and Operation Models for each hub in close collaboration with each of the RPF0s (Mondardini et al, 2022). As part of this task, the RPF0s were asked to reflect on planned activities. This resulted in an overview of envisaged activities as is shown below (Table 1).

Table 1: Proposed activities by the CSHs per RPFO

AUTh	UAB	UT	VG TU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • co-creation; • networking with supporters and collaborators; • matchmaking; • training; • access to support infrastructure (e.g., IT services, research resources and material); • communication and dissemination; • engagement of diverse parts of the community (age, backgrounds, gender etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide resources to facilitate researchers' implementation of CS projects (legal and ethical advice, overview of CS projects, overview of co-creation spaces and tools, CS-methodology, facilitator, apps builder for CS); • provide an internal collaboration space among researchers; • link to other CSHs in Europe; • develop map of CS researchers (via the UAB research portal), develop a CS skills profile and deliver related skills training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication & dissemination; • providing (online) tools & spaces, solutions for data and ethics; • mapping CS initiatives and stakeholders; • building communities and projects; • developing an educational programme and skills training; • increase science literacy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication and dissemination with a focus on awareness raising on RRI, Citizen Science and Open Science principles; • network building and maintenance (with special focus given on sharing the know-how and finding partners with relevant experience, tools); • strengthening international cooperation with partners having experience with RRI, Citizen Science and Open Science; • education and training of the community.

The insights from T2.2 confirm that the CSHs target certain activity clusters:

- Research: Support infra (AUTh), provide resources (UAB), providing tools (UT);
- Awareness & engagement: Co-creation, networking, engagement (AUTh, VG TU), spaces and tools (UAB), creating overviews of initiatives and research(ers) (UAB, UT), building communities (UT), communication and dissemination (UT, VG TU);
- Education: (Skills) Training (AUTh, UAB, UT) and educational programmes (UT).

2.2.4 Learnings from Monitoring & Evaluation Framework

Moving to the last active project action to provide relevant insights for a methodology for defining CSH activities, is part of Task 4.1 that focuses on a Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (M&E framework, Angelidou et al., 2022). This task has defined three objectives enriched with a total of five sub-objectives that allow for local variation in the institutional changes at each of the RPFOS:

1. Grounding RRI in society
 - a. Promoting good practice in citizen science
 - b. Cultivating a more scientifically interested and literate society
 - c. Enhancing fruitful stakeholder interactions
2. Transforming how RPFOS create impact and interact with their surroundings
3. Advancing sustainable development at the local, regional, and global level
 - a. Making progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals
 - b. Creating societal, economic, and democratic scientific impact

As the RPFOS are currently preparing their CSH piloting plans, it is important to have the above objectives in mind when structuring the CSH's monitoring and assessment activities. The M&E framework will perform monitoring and evaluation according to the following methods:

- Method 1: Collection of feedback from CS project participants through CS Project questionnaires;
- Method 2: Collection of data from various CS Hub activities through CS Hub reports;
- Method 3: Collection of data regarding institutional changes through RPFOS reports;
- Method 4: Collection of data on involved citizens' viewpoints through stakeholder interviews.

This implies that many of the actions led by the CSH - or evoked by them - will be monitored and evaluated. When relating this to the definition of the hubs' activities, it is important to realise that actions carried out could be used for data collection moments to contribute to the monitoring and evaluation process. This entails substantial efforts by each of the CSHs (Table 2):

*Table 2: Proposed M&E activities by the CSHs**

M&E target	Tool
The CSH monitor all activities and internal features	Participants to CSH activities complete feedback questionnaire; internal changes reported in CSH report
Each CSH monitors its citizen science projects	Project participants complete project questionnaire (start and end of the project)
The CSH keeps track of developments at the RPFO level	RPFO data collection tool
The CSH interviews its QH stakeholders (following the Most significant Change approach)	Members of the stakeholder board and other internal or external stakeholders are asked to tell their personal stories of how they experienced the most significant change that took place within the RPFO

It was agreed that the RPFOs should consider these M&E activities as indicative.

2.3 Methodology for CSH activities

Having identified the major insights established by the project so far, let's now move to proposing a methodology for CSH activities. CSHs will be new organisations that will develop and evolve over time. We can interpret their development as a phased approach in the diversity of activities from getting started towards the establishment of a permanent base. In the development of the INCENTIVE project, five clusters of activities were envisioned:

- Monitoring and evaluating activities;
- Awareness raising activities;
- R&I co-creation activities;
- Capacity building activities;
- Mutual learning and networking activities.

Each of these clusters will be directly followed-up by the following tasks in the project. The project's Monitoring and Evaluation Framework and CSH performance (1st cluster) will be covered by WP 4 (on Monitoring, evaluation and assessment), whereas clusters 2-5 will directly be targeted by WP3 (on Setting-up and operating the Citizen Science Hubs) including mutual learning across the pilots. When looking at the clusters from the perspective of getting each CSH started up, the clusters can now be better positioned. The respective clusters can be put into a logical order – from getting started to a permanent CSH - leading to the following methodology for CSH activities:

Cluster 1: Monitoring and evaluation

phase: getting started

When getting started, it is important to set the criteria for success. We need to permanently monitor and evaluate (M&E) our CSH's performance to make sure it is serving the needs of all (QH) stakeholders. The continuous feedback we elicit from our stakeholders and participants will allow us to have a reflective dialogue with the community as to make sure that we are meeting their requirements. This phase covers the quality control of a CSH and is a continuing set of activities from getting started to a more permanent CSH.

Outcomes: *local M&E framework including monitoring process, evaluating forms and ways to share with the community.*

Cluster 2: Awareness raising

phase: getting started

Establishing a CSH starts with awareness raising activities. We create a baseline to reach out to our future communities, both inside and outside of each university. This relates to preparing your facilities, team and - in terms of activities - launching the CSH. The core message is that we have started and want to get in touch with prospective community members.

Outcomes: *CSH communication strategy, visual identity and house style; specified in e.g., a website, flyer and video.*

Cluster 3: R&I co-creation

phase: towards a permanent base

Defining your CSH activities - to establish your CSH - starts with R&I co-creation activities. We start with organising public activities allowing us to connect to prospective community members. We want to start to establish a common ground and discuss ideas, needs and interests of the people that will constitute the baseline of our CSH communities. These could be the stakeholder board that most of the CSH anticipate (D2.2). To get some first experience, we propose the co-creation of one or two CS research pilots (also required by the project). In this stage, the establishment of the CSH community space is also relevant. Where will the community meet and how will you stay in touch with them? This requires a communication strategy.

Outcomes: *CSH community strategy including CSH community space, start of two CS research projects.*

Cluster 4: Capacity building

phase: towards a permanent base

Having the first CS projects running, we will scale up in terms of capacity building. We focus on capacity building to be able to move forward towards the permanent base. In this stage, we will be developing pathways for scientific knowledge development and empowering our communities (e.g., skills improvement, networking). Important activities to consider are CS-education (incl. science literacy), CS-methodology, CS-funding & CS-project support. In this stage, it is crucial to move from single projects towards a permanent dialogue with your

community, hence, activities at this stage should allow the community to also bring in their own ideas and projects and increase their capacity (training, tools, guidelines) so they can also organise themselves. The CC-CS has nice examples of how to do this (e.g., the Citizen Science Project Builder).

***Outcomes:** CSH communities, CSH pathways, CSH establishment*

Cluster 5: Mutual learning and networking

phase: a permanent base

Parallel to Stage 3, the CSH will also be more closely connected to related initiatives - both nationally and internationally - to foster mutual learning and networking. Internationalisation is a natural dimension in science, yet in the case of the local and regional communities from society this is less obvious. As a result, this stage might include the scientists more than the non-scientists. It is also a strategic decision to be made by the CSH itself, as we have seen inspiring examples of how international CS projects can be brought to regional non-scientific communities (e.g., iedereenwetenschapper.be)

***Outcomes:** (inter)national CSH pathways, enlarged CSH communities and advanced CSH establishment.*

Table 3: Activity clusters of the CSHs

	Cluster 1: Monitoring and evaluation	Cluster 2: Awareness raising	Cluster 3: R&I co-creation	Cluster 4: Capacity building	Cluster 5: Mutual learning and networking
phase	Getting started	Getting started	Towards a permanent base	Towards a permanent base	Permanent base
What	Monitoring the CSHs performance to meet the community's needs	Encouraging the interest in the CSH activities	Building the community	Increasing the capacity to move towards a permanent base	Enabling the stakeholders of the CSHs to connect and exchange
How	Participant feedback, quality monitoring and permanent reflective dialogue with community	Inviting new participants and increase the interest in (and engage with) science	Bringing society and science together and engaging scientists, citizens and other stakeholders	CS-education (incl. science literacy), CS-methodology, CS-funding and CS-project support ¹ , RPFO's R&I programmes	Providing synergies, alignments and crossovers inside the CSH and between the CSHs

¹ During the piloting phase, the CSH are expected to initiate at least two CS projects

Tools and examples	<p>Monitoring, Evaluation and Assessment Framework</p> <p>Questionnaires and evaluation forms</p> <p>A public year plan</p>	<p>A communication strategy including identification of target audiences; communication tools (website, video, newsletter, social media accounts)</p>	<p>Recurring communication (e.g., newsletter, social media updates) and public events (workshops, science cafes, sprints, seminars, webinars, lectures, pint of science, open days)</p>	<p>Recurring communication and public events</p> <p>CS scientific outputs</p>	<p>Recurring communication, public events and longer-term activities (internships, missions, cross-CSH projects etc.)</p>
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Discerning levels of CSH activities

Above, we discussed the CSH activity clusters in the order of CSH development. Another dimension to consider when defining activities is the level on which they take place. We can discern three major levels of activities:

1. Strategic level: these activities concern giving direction to the CSH as a whole and they relate to making choices and decisions such as deciding on starting funding;
2. Tactical level: these activities concern, for example, establishing the tools, spaces, rooms and getting funding; and
3. Operational level: these activities relate to the day-to-day running of the CSH and encompass the more practical activities. Examples were provided above (webinar, science lectures etc.).

While operational level activities will be the baseline for the CSHs activities, the strategic and tactical levels also need to be considered while moving through the phases of a CSH development.

In this section, we have presented a methodology for defining activities considering the development of the CSH. Getting started with a CSH starts with setting the criteria for success as part of a Monitoring and Evaluating framework followed by – or in parallel to - awareness raising a first cluster of activities relating to stakeholders. Then the community needs to be built as well as the capacity. These clusters will allow to move towards a permanent base that is about mutual learning and networking and where the stakeholders of the CSHs connect and exchange.

3. ACTIVITIES DEFINED BY EACH CITIZEN SCIENCE HUB

Previously in the INCENTIVE project, several activities required input from the piloting RPFs on what activities they envisioned for their CSH. In this chapter, we brought these outcomes together.

3.1 Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

Previously in INCENTIVE AUTH already defined the main (clusters of) activities of their preferred CSH to include:

- Lifelong Learning;
- Data Collection;
- Participatory Science and Partnerships.

To realise this, partnerships were foreseen with local and regional partners (OK!Thess, AUTH's ELKE and KeDiVim initiatives, and the municipality of Thessaloniki) as well as national and EU funding. When bringing the envisioned activities into action, AUTH's preferred CSH has at its core: ethics, involving citizens and supporting CS communities. Research and training are placed at its society intersection. While funding, communication and dissemination, as well as providing CS co-creation spaces, are all seen as happening at the intersection between the CSH and the university.

When turning the preferences into governance structure and operating models as part of T2.2, AUTH added the following to their core activities:

- Co-creation;
- Networking with supporters and collaborators;
- Matchmaking; training; access to support infrastructure (e.g., IT services, research resources and material);
- Communication and dissemination;
- Engagement of diverse parts of the community (age, backgrounds, gender etc.).

With the piloting phase getting closer, the CSHs are further developing their ideas on their activities and how these should be timed in order of development. During a recent Mutual Learning workshop (22 Feb 2022), the activities foreseen by the AUTH CSH team are:

1. **Raise awareness**, examples: Citizen Science Info Days;
2. **CS projects: development and data collection**, examples: Ambition Ranking, Group Knowledge, Open-source hardware and co-creative methods to sense our environment, Ideation activities, Iteration activities, Data analysis;
3. **Stakeholder engagement activities**, examples: Warm ups, Energizers, Outreach, Community building;
4. **Learning curriculum and training activities**, examples: Knowledge sharing, Training/seminars;

5. **Dissemination and outreach**, examples: Website, Newsletters, Local media (radio, tv) engagement, social media.

Being relatively new to institutional change for RRI, AUTH is keen to cover all clusters of activities that were proposed in Chapter 2. It is advised to take time for getting started including tactical and strategic levels of activities as well.

3.2 Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)

In INCENTIVE's Co-creation Workshop, UAB defined the main (clusters of) activities of their preferred CSH to include: 1) Defining Challenges between UAB and Quadruple Helix; 2) Engagement with Stakeholders, and 3) Engaging with New CS Researchers. This will be done through training, network development, coordination, tool provision and sharing good practices of existing CS projects. UAB's core activities will be the following:

- CS project support;
- CS online tools & spaces;
- Communication & Dissemination;
- Training & Education.

Most operational nodes aim to provide overviews, of tools, spaces, initiatives, communities and projects that all relate to CS. At the intersection between society and university, the CSH performs shared agenda setting. Training for citizens and the managing of engagement are part of the CSH, but less of a core operation.

When turning the preferences into governance structure and operating models (T2.2), UAB core activities have been further developed into the following:

- Provide resources to facilitate researchers implementing CS projects (legal and ethical advice);
- Overview of CS projects;
- Overview of co-creation spaces and tools (CS-methodology, facilitators, software);
- Provide an internal collaboration space among researchers, for them to share and exchange experiences and resources;
- Link to other CS Hubs in Europe;
- Develop a CS skills profile and take it into account when delivering skills training.

During a recent Mutual Learning workshop (22 Feb 2022), these are the activities foreseen by the UAB CSH team:

1. **R&I Co-creation activities**: Supporting the implementation of citizen science projects;
2. **Awareness raising activities**, including the development of a Citizen Science page on the institutional website.

3. **Mutual learning and networking activities** enable the stakeholders to connect and exchange knowledge with other stakeholders.
4. **Capacity building activities** on Open Science and Citizen Science addressed different kinds of stakeholders.

Being experienced in fostering RRI, UAB will target not only the getting started clusters of activities that were presented in Chapter 2, but will gradually cover all clusters of activities to establish the CSH into the RPFO.

3.3 University of Twente (UT)

In INCENTIVE's Co-creation Workshop, UT defined the main (clusters of) activities of their preferred CSH to focus on providing support to citizens. More specifically, support should be provided on scientific methods and proving solutions for practical matters for citizens. Citizens coming to the CSH with questions should have ownership and be committed to working towards solutions. An infrastructure is needed that would facilitate and train citizens in scientific methods. UT's preferable CSH has Communication & Dissemination at its core, and this is considered to relate to managing engagement, involving citizens, training, and education of CS skills, and providing CS co-creation spaces and tools, as well as CS project overviews. UT's CSH is envisioned to not execute research itself, but to be the facility to gather knowledge and skills. The researchers may be affiliated with the CSH, but their formal employment will be with their faculty.

When turning the preferences into governance structure and operating models (T2.2), UT's core activities have been further developed into the following:

- Build communities and projects;
- Provide (online) tools, infrastructure & rooms;
- Integrate solutions for data and ethics;
- Map CS initiatives and stakeholders;
- Develop an educational programme and skills training;
- Communication & dissemination.

The UT CSH team emphasised in a recent Mutual Learning Workshop (22 Feb 2022) that its activities should support their aims to become a Centre of expertise. This centre should contribute to excellent science and act as a go-to place for citizens and researchers. This should be realised through a well-balanced operational plan and a supporting communication strategy that defines a set of activities to first raise awareness followed by co-creation and capacity building to become a permanent base for CS.

In terms of fostering RRI into the institution, UT is one of the more experienced RFPOs. UT's CSH has the ambition to become a centre of expertise hence, it will gradually cover all clusters of activities during the upcoming piloting phase.

3.4 Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VGTU)

In INCENTIVE's Co-creation Workshop, VGTU defined the main (clusters of) activities of their preferred CSH to include Research, Awareness & Engagement, Agenda setting and Training & Education. While bringing these activities into practice, the CSH is aiming to include "everyone". Yet, this diversity is also considered to be challenging, bringing up communication issues and conflicting views. Also, a potential lack of interest by both scientists and citizens is considered and structural changes are needed in funding and training.

VGTU's preferred CSH has Training, CS skills and Awareness & Engagement at its core. Doing research preceded by agenda setting is happening both at the borders of the CSH and society, as well as the university. Funding, project support, ethics and dealing with data and involving citizens is placed outside of the CSH at the intersection between university and society. Preferred facilities of the CSH include IT equipment, such as hardware and software, a virtual platform to support the exchange of problems and ideas, project support skills on management, and event organisation and communication. Access to expert tools and knowledge is also deemed necessary.

When turning the preferences into governance structure and operating models (T2.2), VGTU's core activities have been further developed into the following:

- Communication and dissemination with a focus on awareness raising on RRI, Citizen Science and Open Science principles;
- Network building and maintenance (with special focus given to sharing the know-how and finding partners with relevant experience, tools);
- Strengthening international cooperation with partners with experience of RRI, Citizen Science and Open Science; Education and
- Training of the community.

In a recent Mutual Learning Workshop (22 Feb 2022), the VGTU team emphasised wanting to achieve a virtual hub complemented with offline pop-up training activities and seminars. They also aim to become a platform to share insights in Open Science, Citizen Science and RRI and act as network. To achieve this, the CSH will start with dissemination activities (emails, social media) including preparing materials in the national language and training activities.

Fostering RRI into the institution is relatively new to VGTU. Therefore, VGTU will take time on the getting started phase by focusing in particular on awareness raising during the upcoming piloting phase.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this report, we presented a methodology for preparing CSH activities. As activities are ways to raise the CSHs ambitions, we argue that these ambitions should first be defined before preparing the CSH's activities. Furthermore, the character of the activities depends on the development of the CSH, from getting a CSH started towards a more permanent presence of the CSH. The main clusters of activities are the following:

1. Monitoring and evaluation
2. Awareness raising
3. R&I co-creation
4. Capacity building
5. Mutual learning and networking

In addition, we advised to discern the levels of CSH activities being strategic, tactical and operational. While operational level activities (see the above clusters 1-5) will be the baseline for the CSHs activities, the strategic and tactical levels also need to be considered while moving through the phases of a CSH development.

In several stages of the project so far, the piloting RFPOs have provided their input on the activities they prefer, envision or prioritise. The report has gathered these insights and summed them up. Per RPFO, priority will be given to the following activities:

AUTh	Raise awareness, stakeholder engagement activities, learning curriculum and training activities, and dissemination and outreach.
UAB	R&I Co-creation, awareness raising, mutual learning, and networking and capacity building.
UT	Awareness raising, co-creation and capacity building.
VGTU	Dissemination & training.

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ABOUT THE PROJECT

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. The project seeks to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes on how to create and operate their own Hub with the aim to secure a sustainable future.

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